
Assessment of Social Studies Lecturers' Competencies in the Application of ICT Resources for Professional Development in Public Colleges of Education in Jigawa State

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Abstract:

The study intended to Assess Social Studies Lecturers Competency in the Application of ICT Resources for Professional Development in Public Colleges of Education in Jigawa State. The study will be conducted using descriptive survey design, a structured questionnaire will be used to seek the opinion of social studies academic staffs. The population of the study will consist of all the academic staffs of social studies department in COEs in Jigawa state, the participant will be drawn using convenience sampling process from the colleges of education in the state. The data will be analyse using descriptive statistics It is hoped that the findings of this study will give more light for the academic staffs to recognize the importance of using ICT resources in teaching learning process. This if well done will improve the academic staffs to know their level of competencies and how to make adjustment where necessary to agree with global standards.

Keywords: Assessment, Lecturers, Competencies, ICT Resources, Professional Development.

Introduction

In this 21st century, the term “technology” is an important issue in many fields including education. This is because technology has become the knowledge transfer highway in most countries. Technology integration nowadays has gone through innovations and transformed our societies that has totally changed the way people think, work and live (Grabe, 2007). As part of this, schools and other educational institutions which are supposed to prepare students to live in “a knowledge society” need to consider ICT integration in their curriculum (Ghavifekr, Afshari & Amla Salleh, 2012).

Integration of Information, Communication, and Technology (ICT) in education refers to the use of computer-based communication that incorporates into daily classroom instructional process. In conjunction with preparing students for the current digital era, teachers are seen as the key players in using ICT in their daily classrooms. This is due to the capability of ICT in providing dynamic and proactive teaching-learning environment (Arnseth & Hatlevik, 2012). While, the aim of ICT integration is to improve and increase the quality, accessibility cost-efficiency of the delivery of instruction and professional development to teachers and students, it also refers to benefits from networking the learning communities to face the challenges of current globalization (Albirini, 2006). Process of adoption of ICT is not a single step, but it is ongoing and continuous steps that fully support teaching and learning and information resources (Young, 2003).

ICT integration in education generally means technology-based teaching and learning process that closely relates to the utilization of learning technologies in schools. Due to the fact that students are familiar with technology and they will learn better within technology-based environment, the issue of ICT integration in schools, specifically in the classroom is vital. This is because, the use of technology in education contributes a lot in the pedagogical aspects in which the application of ICT will lead to effective learning with the help and supports from ICT elements and components (Jamieson-Procter et al., 2013). It is right to say that almost all ranges of subjects’ start from mathematics, science, languages, arts and humanistic and other major fields can be learned more effectively through technology-based tools and equipment. In addition, ICT provides the help and complementary supports for both teachers and students where it involves effective learning with the help of the computers to serve the purpose of learning aids (Jorge et al., 2003). Computers and technology do not act as a replacing tool for quality teachers but instead they are considered as an add-on supplements needed for the better teaching and learning. The need for ICT integration in education is crucial, because with the help of technology, teaching and learning is not only happening in the school environment, but also can happen even if teachers and students are physically in distance. However, ICT integration is not a one-step learning process, but it is a continual process of learning that provides proactive teaching-learning environment (Young, 2003).

In Jigawa state, there are two colleges of education, namely Jigawa State Colleges of Education Gumel and Jigawa State College of Education and Legal Studies Ringim. All of them are using ICT in one form or the other in either admission exercise, payment of school fees, course registration and computation of results. It was on this basis that this study seeks to Assess social studies Lecturers Competencies in the Application of ICT Resources for Professional Development.

Statement of the problems

Tertiary institutions all over the world are complex organizations that replicate and integrate much of the activities in the larger society. They have the capacity to carry out teaching, training and research; and this mandate is enshrined in a complex process with numerous activities which include teaching, training, administration, examination and evaluation. Data and information generated by human race have risen to a proportion that manual manipulation cannot give accurate result. Delivery of educational services, proper record keeping, administrative and managerial services can no longer survive the traditional methods. The problems of information explosion, increase in school enrolment at all levels, shortage of competent and qualified personnel, storage and retrieval of data, high price or resource materials have compelled all institutions, especially tertiary institutions, to evolve means of tackling the problems (Egbowon and Nwaboku, 2009).

The teaching and learning are plagued by plethora of challenges. Both lecturers and students are still trusting on textbook data and class verbalization due to general poor attitude towards innovation. Both lecturers and students also believe that government has neglected education. Consequently, it is observed that many lecturers are yet to fully utilize ICT for effective teaching and learning. Despite the fact that federal and state government have made attempts at building/ rehabilitating colleges of education in the country, motivating lecturers through in-service training (workshop, seminars, conferences etc) is often not emphasized. As a consequence, there is a minimal application of ICT techniques in the teaching and learning process in higher institutions of learning in the state. Therefore, the focus of this research examines the role of ICT in improving teaching and learning process in COEs in Jigawa State. In support of this, Yusuf, Afolabi & Loto, (2013) has this to say, a daunting challenge facing the education system is the lack of competent teachers who are literate and proficient in the use of computer application, computer packages and information technology.

Objectives of the study

1. To measure the level of using Microsoft word for professional development.
2. Assess the lecturers' level of using Microsoft excel for professional development.
3. To assess the lecturer's level of using power point for professional development in the study area.
4. Measure the level of using internet for professional development in the study area

Literature Review

Information Technology is the term used to cover a whole range of hardware and software. Information Technology (IT) system processes, stores, and/or transfers (communicates) information. IT merges computing with high-speed communications links carrying data, sound and video. Examples include personal computers, telephones, television and various handheld devices (Williams and Sawyer, 2005). Computers and communications are the pivots of Information Technology (IT).

To transfer information, Information Technology (IT) systems use computers, telecommunications networks, and other electronic devices. Thus, the addition of the word 'communication' is inevitable. Hence, we have Information and Communication Technology (ICT). When information and communication assume drifts away from the orthodox verbal and print media towards the more recent electronic media, the concept is known as Information and Communication Technology (ICT). Thus, ICT could be seen as the combination of networks, hardware and software as well as the means of communication,

collaboration and engagement that enable the processing, management and exchange of data, information and knowledge (Mahmud et al 2018). The term 'ICT' is often preferred to 'IT'. The basis of ICT, however, is simply to help improve the way we deal with information in all areas of life.

According to Pearson (2013) "ICT is a scientific, technological and engineering discipline and management technique used in handling information, its application and association with social, economic and cultural matters". Teacher is the main part of the educational field in our society. In the context of the school curriculum, the term Information and Communications Technology (ICT) is used to refer to a range of tools and techniques relating to computer-based hardware, to communications including both directed and broadcast, to information sources such as CD-RUM and the internet, and to associated technologies such as robots, videoconferencing and digital TV (Collis et al 2013).

This is an all-embracing description. It marries both the old Information Technology to the new innovation made possible by communication process to enhance effective information and communication network. The development in technology has turned the world into a global village and information is now being processed at very fast speed with highly sophisticated equipment. Through ICT, the whole world is reduced to a unit and any part of the world could be reached in a split of second. ICT consists of a diverse but cohesive set of computer-related technologies used in handling information, from its generation to ultimate dissemination (Tor, Shiekuma, Olatunji and Adisa, 2020).

The Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework is a schematic interpretation of the lecturers' ICT competence skills and job effectiveness in university. The conceptual framework explains the process by which the study will be carried out, and explains the interactions between the independent and dependent variables of the study. The overall conceptual framework of the major concepts of the study is presented in the conceptual frame work figure.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study
 Source: adopted from Suleiman (2024)

Review of Related Empirical Studies

Several empirical studies are conducted in this area, the study conducted by Gulber & Guven (2008) on the Survey on ICT Usage and the Perception of Social Studies Teachers in Turkey. The research has nine objectives, the population used in this research was 326 teachers and also convenience sampling techniques was used. In the instrumentation discussion method was used, and the research design was survey in nature.

Another research was carried out by Anyim (2018), he researched on ICT literacy skills of digital users and staff in Saleem university Lokaja, Kwara state. He used descriptive research design. The population of the research is 53 lecturers. All the population of the research formed the sample size, questionnaire and checklist were employed for data collection. The research is similar to the present study in terms of research technique. However, the major difference is in the research area, the sample size.

Methodology

For the purpose of this research, two colleges of education will form the population of the study that is Jigawa State College of Education Gumel and College of Education and Legal studies Ringim. Therefore, all the academic staffs in Social Studies Department of the said colleges will make the sample, hence convenience sampling procedure was adopted. As

such, there are eleven (11) lecturers in JSCOE Gumel, while College of Education and Legal Studies Ringim had eight (8) academic staffs. Therefore, nineteen (19) will formed the population for this study. The study will employ survey research design to enable the researchers get first – hand observation of variables in the study.

Qualitative research is well-suited for understanding the subjective experiences and perspectives of participants. The design will involve the use of questionnaire to the academic staffs in the selected area. The collected data was analysed using descriptive statistics. This will be to determine the equivalent and variability in their competencies.

Results and Discussion

1. The first objective of the study is to Measure the level of using Microsoft word for professional development in the study area. Table 1 summarizes the

Findings:

Table 1: Competency in using Microsoft word

Statement	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Turning 'ON' computer	Yes	18	95%
	No	01	5%
Opening Microsoft word	Yes	18	95%
	No	01	5%
Typing lecture note in the computer	Yes	15	78%
	No	04	21%
Using numeric symbols in typing	Yes	10	53%
	No	09	47%
Inserting pictures in writing	Yes	09	47%
	No	10	53%

The data in table 1 above shows that 95% of the academic staffs are of the habit of using Microsoft word for professional development. with 78% of the sample attesting that they typed lecture note themselves. More so, 53% of the respondents in the study area participate in using numeric symbols and pictures for professional development. It was also found that less than 5% of the respondents are not using Microsoft word for professional development.

Table 2: Competency in Using Microsoft Excel

Statement	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Using excel to compute students result	Yes	07	36%
	No	12	63%
Using excel in storage of student data	Yes	06	32%
	No	13	68%
Using excel to insert row and columns	Yes	05	26%
	No	14	74%
Using excel in organising data list	Yes	10	53%
	No	09	47%
Using excel in managing data list	Yes	08	42%
	No	11	59%

The data in table 2 above shows that only 36% of the academic staffs are of the habit of using Microsoft excel to compute results. with 63% of the sample attesting that they don't use excel in results computation. Additionally, 32% of the respondents stored student's data using excel, while 68% do not stored data. It was also found that 26 % of the respondents are not using Microsoft excel for professional development.

Table 3: Competency in using PowerPoint

Statement	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Using power point in lecture presentation	Yes	02	11%
	No	17	89%
Using power point in conference presentation	Yes	17	89%
	No	02	11%
Using power point in results presentation	Yes	17	89%
	No	02	11%
Using power point in class tutorial presentation	Yes	10	53%
	No	09	47%
Using power point in displaying pictures	Yes	05	26%
	No	14	74%

The data in table 3 above shows that 89% of the lecturers are not using PowerPoint during lecture presentations. with 11% of the lecturers are defaulters. Meanwhile, 89% are using PowerPoint in conferences and results presentations. It was also instituted that 53 % are using PowerPoint in tutorial, with 47% not using PowerPoint in tutorial. Less than 26% are not using PowerPoint for professional development.

Table 4: Competency in using internet

Statement	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Connecting to the internet	Yes	19	100%
	No	00	00%
Sending an e- mail message	Yes	15	79%
	No	04	21%
Using www search engine e.g Google	Yes	19	100%
	No	00	00%
Downloading files from internet	Yes	17	89%
	No	02	11%
Uploading publications online	Yes	08	42%
	No	11	58%

With regards to table 4 above, the result shows that 100% of the academic staffs engage in the use of internet and search engines for professional development respectfully. While 89% download files from internet for professional development. Moreover, 79% of the respondents are sending mails massages. The least is 11% cannot download files. In another development, 58% do not upload their publication online, while only 42% upload their publication online.

To sum it up, these findings revealed that majority of the academic staffs have a knowledge on the application of ICT for professional development in the public colleges of education in Jigawa state.

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